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Designing Inclusive Classroom and Collaboration: A Panacea for Effective Instruction for Students with Hearing Impairment in Nigeria

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Citation: Owobi, E. A. & Magaji, R. A. (2026). Designing Inclusive Classroom and Collaboration: A Panacea for Effective Instruction for Students with Hearing Impairment in Nigeria. *Nas. State Uni. J. of Spe. & Inclusive Edu;* 1(1), 207–215. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19564546>

Academic Editor: Dr. Jummai Jerry

Received: 14 November, 2025

Revised: 8 December, 2025

Accepted: 3 February, 2026

Published: 1 April, 2026

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Abstract: *This study focused on designing inclusive classroom and collaboration: Panacea for effective instructions for deaf students with hearing loss in Nigeria. Designing an effective inclusive classroom and collaboration has serious relevance for deaf students with hearing loss if high-quality education is been provided. Recently, the inclusion of students with hearing impairment in Nigeria has triggered wide acceptance and attention on a philosophical level among stakeholders. The paper explained that inclusive Classroom perception is a key variable for effective instruction for deaf students with hearing loss. The authors further detailed that if inclusive classroom dimensions are provided, this makes instruction easy for these students. Also, the paper ex-rayed community and social sense of inclusive acceptance. Again, the researchers detailed inclusive classroom diversity of deaf students in inclusive classroom as one of key inclusive collaborations, effective management and instruction in inclusive classroom was thoroughly debated and discussed as the bases for designing inclusive classroom and collaboration for effective instruction of students with hearing impairment.*

Keywords: Designing Inclusive Classroom, Inclusive Education, Classroom Collaboration, Effective Instruction and Hearing Impairment

Introduction

Before now, the critical challenge underlying successful inclusion of students with hearing impairment with their peers in regular classroom setting, is the acceptance of diversities. This philosophical assumption is rooted on the premises of societal and parental negativity of the causes about hearing loss. However, the recent inclusion of deaf students who have hearing loss in inclusive classrooms continuous to receive significant attention on a philosophical level. This wide acceptance has shifted the deep-rooted assumptions that detach and track deaf students with hearing loss with the assumption that in every disability there is ability and a level of achievements. The concepts of inclusion education provide that students with hearing loss can be engage, value and also, can participate actively in an inclusive setting if high-quality education is provided through a designed environment with the alliance of relevant curriculum, cogent teaching, and requisite supports. Inclusion is obviously different from the ideas of normalization or integration, where students with hearing loss are put together in the physical proximity with their hearing counterpart, but no significant regard is accorded to such a setting or arrangement.

The United States Department of Education (U.S) 2019 asserts that designing an effective inclusive classroom and collaboration have relevance for students with hearing loss short-time objectives as well as long-term objective. These short-term objectives include the needs to learn alongside with hearing counterparts or peers in a classroom. (Learning activities), while in the long-term objective, deaf students with hearing loss are expected to carry out the same assignments with their hearing counterparts in their home environment. The United States Department of Education (U.S) concludes that if deaf students with hearing loss are not given the opportunity to mixed and learn with their hearing counterparts, they may not be able to accomplish their short-time and long-time objective in live. Owobi (2022) argued that deafness is a hearing impairment condition which can affects the entire personality of an individual, especially, when it is post-natal in nature. The author debits that hearing loss is an inability for one to hear sounds, or distinguishes a particular sound from other sounds, also that hearing loss often results in problems with speech and language development. He therefore, noted that the effects of hearing impairment are so pervasive and destructive that interferes not only with the

student's education but also with his or her emotional adjustment and personality organization.

In this study therefore, the writers posited their discussion on the following:

1. Inclusive Classroom perception.
2. Inclusive classroom dimensions.
3. Community and social sense of inclusive acceptance.
4. Inclusive classroom diversity of deaf students
5. Effective management and instruction in inclusive classroom
6. Recommendation
7. Conclusion

Inclusive Classroom perception

Idea of inclusive classroom perception of deaf students with hearing loss is been perceived differently by teachers, parents and the society at large. Most teachers often expressed their lack of disapproval and unwillingness to teach deaf students with hearing loss. Some of these negative responses stem from difficulties teachers faced passing instruction due to lack of expertise training skills, lack of supportive services and resources to enable them work effectively with deaf students. These notions coincide with the comment of Roach (2020) who posited that teachers' inability to cope with deaf students with hearing loss in inclusive classroom are not predisposed on the philosophy of inclusive education itself but anchored on teachers' personal negative perception about difficulties learning the requisites skill in teaching deaf students with hearing loss. Also, parents' perception about inclusive classroom varies, so many parents with normal students have negative disapproval toward inclusive nature. Some of these reasons are; deafness is an infectious disease, stigmatization and ignorant. Furthermore, some proponents of inclusive education provide a glimpse of the tasks faced for teaching deaf students with hearing loss in an inclusive setting (Westling, 2018). According to the author, any class that calls for inclusion of deaf students with hearing loss must have adequate support service (interpreters) and conducive learning environment.

Inclusive classroom dimensions

There are five essential features that characterized effective inclusion of deaf students with hearing loss, these includes: Community and social sense of acceptance; students diversity appreciation; curricular attention needs, managing instruction effectively and support and collaboration of personnel. Lending credence to these assertions Hobb (2018) noted that when these are put in place, inclusiveness becomes

effective.

Inclusive Education Model versus Traditional Special Education Model

S/N	Traditional Model	Inclusive Education Model
1.	Few students 'fit into' inclusive classroom	All students 'fit into' in general classroom
2.	Teacher is the instructor leader	Collaboration and teams share tasks
3.	Students only listen, while teachers talk	Students and teachers learn from each other's
4.	Students learning abilities are not considered	students learning differences are taking into consideration
5.	Instruction targeted average students	Instruction targeted all students of achievement levels
6.	Curricular content is limited to Grade-level placement	Curricular content is independent of each other
7.	Instruction is sometime passive, competitive, didactic, based on teacher's directive	Instruction is collaborative and it activeness, creativity are all involving
8.	Some instructional supports are not provided in the classroom	All instructional supports are provided in the classroom.
9.	Most students who cannot 'fit in' are excepted from general classroom	Activities designation includes all level of students through participation.
10.	Normal teacher takes ownership of classroom for educating hearing students, while special teachers assume ownership for the education of deaf students with hearing loss.	All teachers, to include; special educators, related service staff, assume ownership for educating all students.
11.	Students are evaluated without a standard test.	Students are evaluated individually using a standard test
12.	All students' success is obtained by common standards	The education system is considered successful as it meets each student's targeted objective.

Hobb (2018)

Community and social sense of inclusive acceptance.

For any inclusive classroom setting to be efficacious, all deaf students with hearing loss are appreciated and nurtured. Such a classroom settings need to advance equal treatment for deaf students with hearing loss, give each one of them the advantage or benefit to contribute in the learning process and their ideas must be respected. Inclusive classroom can also be effective when deaf students with hearing loss are acknowledged by their teachers and socially assented by their classmates. To establish successful inclusive classroom, teachers need to poses these three qualities; Teachers attitude toward deaf students, teachers' knowledge of skills in teaching deaf students and teachers' qualification.

Supporting this view, Schulz (2015) submitted that these three qualities must aligned with deaf students' interest, their physical and behavior characteristics, and other related learning experiences require in the teaching of deaf students with hearing loss. Furthermore, the author posited that there is the need for deaf students to poses two competences to enable them function effectively in an inclusive classroom setting; first, the knowledge of precise information and its effect on their hearing classmates; second, peer fundamental interactions for informal development which often led to peer support. Deno, and Espin (2019) ascribe to an ideal inclusive classroom setting as a warmth setting with a strong community sense of belongingness where diversification and esteem are adequately address.

Inclusive classroom diversity of deaf students

In maximizing inclusive classroom environment, understanding deaf student individual differences cannot be overemphasis. Teachers must take into cognizance deaf student individual learning need, recognizing deaf students' individual educational goal, sensitive to deaf students cultural and community needs, as well as their family values. Schwartz and Karge (1996) distinguished deaf students' differences as follows: Racial and ethnic differences; gender and sexual predilection; religious variegate; physical, learning, and metaphysical differences; lingual differences; comportment and personality diversity. The authors expound to say that diversity is enriching, where deaf students with hearing loss can flourish and where privileges are provided for them and their individual differences are recognized and appreciated.

Classroom environment which promoted inclusive setting, should ensure that deaf students' individual differences are taking into consideration. These differences should include; learning, physical, emotional, and social needs which varies based on the onset and degree of loss and even with their hearing counterparts. Teachers must also take note of adequate support services that can help address differences to make teaching and learning effective. Teacher should also teach deaf students to tolerance and accept differences in others as well as cooperative learning and ability to adjust to instructional strategies.

Also, for teachers to be able to pay adequate attention to curricular needs of deaf students with hearing loss, their educational placement must be scrutinized where deaf students learning and life needs must be driven toward programmatic goals. Based on this premise, Williams (2022) is of the view that if deaf students with hearing loss are involve inclusively in classroom activities, they can adjust to any curricula changes effectively. The author pointed out that such curricula contents should comprise; content that is significance to student current and future sense, and approaches and materials that can work best for deaf students' current and future sense. Also, the author of the view that deaf students are require to learn knowledge and skills acquisition in order to expand their horizon of the curricular content. On this principle, teachers are expected to modify the curricular content to help them focus more on functional objectives and guide deaf students the ability to demonstrate mastery of the curricula contents.

Effective management and instruction in inclusive classroom

Setting inclusive classroom is an essential component of inclusive practices which enhances conducive learning environment for deaf students with hearing loss. These inclusive practices involve four elements, they are; successful classroom management, effective instructional technique, appropriate accommodative practices, and instructional flexibility. Effective inclusion classrooms which encourage learning are characterized by a sound organizational and management system. This inclusive classroom management- include physical, procedural, instructional, behavior management; these help teachers to set the stage for the smooth delivery of teaching and impressive body of content that encourage to validate the effectiveness of certain instructional practices. Brody and Good (2006), Welch (2007)

itemized relevant key elements of these effective instructional practices, they include daily review, and specific strategies for presenting new information, guided practice, independent practice and formative evaluation. The authors further explained that for inclusive classroom to be effective, the following are expected to be put in place.

a. Structure: Teachers should have an overview of new content, follow stated objective carefully and ensure that deaf student with hearing loss have the knowledge of sequence and purpose of the presentation

b. Clarity: The teacher should avoid unnecessary deviation, but to ensure to use a clearly defined example. Provide examples such as non-instances of new concepts, use simple, direct language, avoid vague statement (e.g. “a thing like this,” “and so on,” “you know”).

c. Redundancy: Teachers should encourage deaf students to interpret, see, and/or experience new ideas severally. Repeated signs should be allowed to enhance vocabularies or terminologies improvement of deaf students, teachers should reinforce new learning situation, and allows deaf students to practice and share their understanding by predicting what the teachers are to say based on the previous learning experiences.

d. Enthusiasm: Teachers should encourage deaf students to pay more attention, show more interest and learn more things especially when the teacher is enthusiastic. This encourages stimulation and arouses deaf students’ curiosity toward a new subject

e. Appropriate pace: Teachers should monitor deaf students whether the content taught is been understood so that the teacher can proceed either swiftly or adjust the speed of the teaching strategy.

f. Maximize engagement: Teachers should know that deaf students with hearing loss learn best when they are directly engaged with the teacher, therefore, teachers should discourage passively listening teaching approach, but be involve in asking more questions directly related to the learning situation. Deaf students can ask direct questions about the teacher presentation (e.g., “What did we say was the major difference between the two stories we have read? Teachers are requested to asks application questions to test deaf students comprehension (e.g., “Give me an example of an insulator that you can see in the classroom); and prompt reasoning to encourage tell us about those dinosaurs?);

and as deaf students answer questions, the teacher should appreciate the correctness of response or quality of the thought, give corrective feedback on any part of the response that needs correction, and ask the question again later. The teacher is expected to use these responses to guide his or her instructional delivery.

Conclusion

Serious task is today being faced for teaching deaf students with hearing loss in various schools where inclusive education is been practice. For inclusive classroom to be effective, there is the need for adequate support services, like sign language interpreters, conducive classroom management. Today the overwhelming acceptance that of deaf students with hearing loss have tragically change most stakeholders in the field of special education the deep-rooted assumption of the ability in disability. The concept of inclusion education, is distinctly different from the notion of integration or mainstreaming, where deaf students with hearing loss are aligned in physical proximity to their hearing counterparts, but without a significant attention toward their qualitative features of their disabilities.

Designing inclusive classroom and collaboration toward high-quality instructions for deaf students with hearing loss cannot be compromises in Nigeria present educational goals. Therefore, there is the need for appropriate curricular content to be develop, adequate support services be provided or available, and teachers should assume their responsibilities to modify their academic curricular contents for instructing deaf students with hearing loss in their various classroom setting, and try to be more focus on functional objectives.

Recommendation

The authors proffered the following recommendations

1. Teachers teaching deaf students with hearing loss should be train with adequate requisite skill to help them function in an inclusive classroom effectively.
2. Curricular content for deaf students in an inclusive classroom should be breakdown to accommodate individual differences.
3. Good teaching and learning environment should be provided in order to promote inclusiveness of deaf students with hearing loss

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